

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE AND STRESS FACTORS OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN THE MODERN ERA

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Abstract: This article analyzes the current psychological state of student youth, their views on the characteristics of significant educational influence, and scientifically based opinions. It examines the current state, problems, and possibilities of utilizing these insights in the spiritual development of the younger generation. Additionally, scientifically grounded recommendations are proposed to achieve more effective results in implementing these concepts in the educational process.

Keywords: "Express your opinion", "Try to compare", "Feel free", psychological, state, student, youth.

Introduction: Youth, particularly student youth, are a crucial subjective factor that ensures the future development of society. Student youth are important members and leaders of the intelligentsia - the social stratum that is most engaged with the social phenomena occurring in society. Their consciousness, goals, social needs, and the values they adhere to influence the social environment, mood, and ideals of society.

The youth stratum consists of the following groups: working youth, student youth, youth in education, unemployed youth, unorganized youth, and migrant youth.

The sustainable development of a society, the interconnectedness of generations, and the transmission of national heritage to the future are largely dependent on the values selected and practiced by its members. Accordingly, it is necessary to pay close attention to issues such as the axiological upbringing of young people, the values they follow in their lives, and the values they are abandoning. Based on the foregoing, a socio-philosophical analysis of the issues related to which values today's Uzbek student youth prefer and practice is a significant theoretical and practical problem.

"Axiological orientation" refers to the values related to the economic, social, political, cultural, spiritual, moral, and aesthetic spheres chosen and preferred by members of society and social groups. These values are considered a social phenomenon that holds a certain significance in their social lives and activities, providing direction and becoming the fundamental principles of their lives.

The majority of Uzbekistan's population consists of young people. At the beginning of 2023, the number of young people reached 19.6 million, equivalent to 60% of the population. Youth are a vital resource for the country, and the future of the society and the nation depends on them.

Youth constitute a distinct social stratum in society. This stratum is an ethnic and socio-demographic group distinguished by the characteristics of the youth period, its social position in society, the functions it performs, and its specific activities. It is characterized by the experience of passing through a period of maturation and formation as an individual. There are

various approaches to defining the age range of youth as a social group. Specialists in this field - sociologists, psychologists, demographers, and others - note that the period of youth generally begins at the age of 14-16 and ends at 25-30.

The educational activities of young people reflect their aspirations and efforts to develop as individuals and acquire a profession. From a psychological perspective, this period is characterized by features such as striving to find one's place in society, seeking to understand the meaning of life by developing a sense of "self," and testing oneself in these processes.

There are various approaches to studying the characteristics and societal position of the group that constitutes youth, as well as its examination as a distinct social group. The choice of approach in this regard depends on the research's objectives and its scientific-practical goals. These can include the following approaches: biological, psychological, social, philosophical, demographic, and so on. The characterization of this social group as "youth" has been specific to different eras. In this context, determining the boundary between young people and older or elderly individuals has also been undertaken based on various approaches and theories. This is because, depending on the characteristics of the historical period, their age levels also differed.

When studying the period of youth from a socio-philosophical perspective, it can be understood as a period full of potential - an evolutionary, dialectical progression of human life from simple to complex, a step-by-step striving towards the future based on the pursuit of one's goals and dreams. From an axiological point of view, the most beautiful period of a person's life, youth, and the subjects experiencing it - young people themselves - are a tremendous social value.

The period of youth is distinguished from other stages of human life by its relative instability, the constant striving of young people, their preparation to master a profession, their efforts to secure a social place and status, and the instability of their values, which in many cases strongly reflects a sense of dissatisfaction.

Considering the mobility of young people and the fact that they are a dynamic group, along with their axiological consciousness, the constant flux of their values, and their inherently dynamic nature, we can understand that they are fundamentally different from other social groups in society, such as adults, the middle-aged, and others.

The listed groups are distinguished from each other conceptually, and there is no rigid boundary between them. These groups are characterized by high dynamics, and the youth within them can also be differentiated from one another in terms of their potential, based on their social position, role, and function in society. The philosopher-scholar Q. Nazarov describes youth as follows: "Youth is a socio-demographic group experiencing the formation and establishment of a spiritual worldview, undergoing fundamental social growth, intensive socialization and adaptation, and reaching social and psychophysiological maturity. The distinct socio-psychological profile of youth is determined by the general condition of society, the principles of socialization, and the opportunities for education and upbringing."

The study of the period of youth and young people from a socio-philosophical perspective must be conducted in the context of their socialization. In this process, phenomena with a dual nature emerge. It is natural for a member of society - each subject - to become socialized as a result of their activities and participation in various spheres of society. This subject, in turn, through their social activity, influences the transformation of certain aspects of society. Such

influence is exerted differently by each subject. Of course, in this case, their engagement and lack of indifference are of great importance.

Youth is the social group that defines the future of society by ensuring the continuity, succession, and interconnectedness of generations. "Youth is an objective social phenomenon, a large and distinct social group that constitutes a part of society. Consequently, the problems of youth are the problems of society as a whole. The relationship between society and youth is the dialectical connection between the whole and its part: by studying a developing society, we can create the necessary conditions for them; by analyzing young people with all their problems and contradictions, we can understand the future development trends of society."

The goals, aspirations, needs, and ideals of all representatives of the youth stratum are similar. Their tasks, behaviors, and problems are also similar to one another. The category "youth" can be applied to all generations. Their period of youth and age are nearly the same. The only difference is that, as a generation, young people in different eras have experienced different socio-historical conditions and social relations. They have performed different functions, and their role in society has also varied depending on the characteristics of the period. If we approach youth as a social group, they have been the primary object of state policy concerning social development and youth throughout all historical periods of societal development.

Literature Review: In addressing the issue of youth, I.S. Kon utilized the concept of "generation," and also employed concepts such as contemporaries, people born at approximately the same time, a stage in an era defined by common ancestry, and the period of birth of parents and children. Currently, unique approaches to studying the problems of youth are emerging, stemming from the demands of the time.

Research Methodology: The emergence of new, modern approaches to the problem under study indicates that the youth stratum (or social group) is becoming increasingly socially active in the current period.

Whereas until this period, youth were analyzed as a stage of a generation, a specific social force, or a subjective factor, today it is clear that the role of youth in the life of society has become extremely active, with their activities being noticeable in all spheres. From this perspective, when considered theoretically, they should be analyzed as disseminators of innovation in society, possessors of intellectual potential, and an active subjective factor in the reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan.

When discussing youth, it is necessary to consider the historical period and historical context in which they lived, which have their own unique characteristics. The traces of all historical periods are manifested in the behavior, character, and appearance of young people. The activities and needs of youth are connected to the demands and needs of the era. In particular, in the age of modern information technologies, ..."youth is an objective social phenomenon, a unique large social group that constitutes a part of society."

Analysis and Results: In keeping with the spirit of the times, it is required to foster an engaged stance towards pressing social issues by properly guiding their consciousness, worldview, and needs, and to direct their existing potential toward solving these problems. A correct axiological relationship lies at the foundation of such processes. This is because every event taking place in society holds not only social but also axiological significance for young people. It is important for young people to comprehend that phenomena emerging in society

and acquiring social relevance affect society and people's lives, and that their proper resolution serves to satisfy the social needs of society and further instill the principles of democracy and humanism in the country. This understanding also increases the country's attractiveness to young people.

It is known that during pivotal periods of social development, the relationships that form in all spheres take on a distinctive character. Correctly perceiving them and, when necessary, adopting a positive or negative attitude towards them, enhances the progressive aspects of these phenomena and positively influences their more rapid dissemination.

Correctly understanding the essence of new social phenomena and relations, properly orienting them based on societal needs, and making purposeful use of them will further elevate the role of youth as a subjective factor in the social development of society.

Conclusion: As societal development accelerates and becomes more complex, one of the problems that arises in this process and is repeatedly placed on the agenda is the values that young people adhere to and their axiological orientation. The problem of the axiological orientation of youth has always existed at all historical stages of human development and in the life of various societies. This problem can be regarded, in essence, as the problem of determining future development and correctly identifying its promising directions and dynamics.

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